

A Prospective Randomized Comparative Assessment of Intravenous Magnesium Sulphate and Lignocaine in Attenuation of Pressor Response to Laryngoscopy and Endotracheal Intubation

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to compare the efficacy of intravenous Magnesium sulphate with intravenous Lignocaine hydrochloride in attenuation of cardiovascular responses to laryngoscopy and intubation.

Methods: It was Prospective Randomized Double-Blind Study on 100 patients done at Department of Anesthesiology at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India. The patients were randomly allocated into two groups, 50 patients in each group. Patients belonging to Group A received 1.5mg/kg of lignocaine intravenously 90 seconds prior to laryngoscopy and intubation. In Group B patients received intravenous magnesium sulphate 30mg/kg, 90 seconds prior to laryngoscopy and intubation.

Results: The result showed the age distribution in Lignocaine (Group A) and Magnesium (Group B) groups. The age range is 20-60 years in both the groups. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups with regard to age and so they are comparable. ($p=0.60$). Samples are gender matched with $P=0.55$. In group A 74% of the patients are male and 26% are females. In group B 70% of the patients are males and 30% are females. Both the Groups are comparable with respect to gender. Intergroup comparison between the two groups showed that the SBP at 1, 5 and 10 minute after laryngoscopy in magnesium group were statistically significantly lower compared to lignocaine group ($P<0.05$). At 3 minute SBP was lower in magnesium group but not statistically significant when compared with lignocaine group. In Magnesium group the post induction DBP values was significantly lower compared to its baseline with P value of 0.02. At 1 minute there was slight increase in mean DBP with $P=0.03$ which returned near baseline value by 3minute. At 5 min and 10 minutes values were significantly lower ($P=0.02$ and $P=0.001$ respectively) when compared to its baseline but this decrease was not clinically significant.

Conclusion: Intravenous magnesium sulphate 30mg/kg 90 seconds prior to laryngoscopy and intubation is superior to lignocaine 1.5mg/kg prior to laryngoscopy and intubation.

Keywords: Intravenous Magnesium Sulphate, Lignocaine Hydrochloride.

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Introduction

Endotracheal intubation is an essential component of general anesthesia. It serves in the maintenance of patency of upper airway, proper ventilation, reduction in the risk of aspiration, and delivery of the inhalational anesthetic agents to the patients through breathing circuits. [1] Laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation are considered the most critical events during induction of general anesthesia which stimulate somatic and visceral nociceptive afferents fibers which induce reflex sympato-adrenal responses associated with enhanced neuronal activity in the cervical sympathetic efferent fibers. [2]

Sympathetic stimulation from laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation causes a significant increase in the plasma concentration of catecholamines (adrenaline and noradrenaline) [3,4] that can provoke left ventricular failure, renal failure, surgical bleeding, cerebral hemorrhage and myocardial ischemia in anesthetized patients. The mechanism of this may be that, vasoconstriction, increased myocardial work, a demand for increased coronary flow, narrowed coronary arteries cannot accommodate the increased flow, and parts of the myocardium may receive insufficient oxygen. [5-7]

The procedures of laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation are not only used in the operating room, but also in non-anaesthetic situations. Diagnostic laryngoscopy and fiberoptic bronchoscopy are two examples of situations where intubation may be required to prevent aspiration and protect the airway, as well as during mechanical ventilation. All of these operations can cause sympathetic responses, and it's important to remember that many of these patients are extremely

ill and at risk. As a result, it's critical to find a way to reduce the sympathetic reaction to laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation. Many treatments focused at different levels of the reflex arc have been advised to reduce these deleterious hemodynamic effects. [8] Topical administration and injection of local anaesthetic to the superior laryngeal nerve to block peripheral sensory receptors and afferent input. Anesthetics, narcotics, alpha 2 receptor agonists, and other drugs block central mechanisms of integration and sensory information. Blockade of efferent pathway and effector sites i.v. lignocaine, beta blockers, calcium channel blockers, hydralazine etc. No single drug or technique is satisfactory. Deep anaesthesia, topical anaesthesia, use of ganglion blockers, beta blockers, antihypertensive drugs such phentolamine, sodium nitroprusside, nitroglycerine, calcium channel blockers are some of the approaches used to reduce intubation-related stress responses. Clonidine, an agonist for the adrenoreceptor, reduces the adrenergic hemodynamic stress response. [9]

The purpose of this study was to see how efficient intravenous lignocaine and magnesium sulphate were at reducing the haemodynamic response to the powerful stimulation of laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation.

Materials and Methods

It was Prospective Randomized Double-Blind Study done at department of Anesthesiology, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India. Present clinical comparative study of IV Lignocaine and IV Magnesium Sulphate in the attenuation of sympathetic response to laryngoscopy and intubation

was done. General anesthesia with endotracheal intubation was provided. 100 Patients scheduled for various elective surgical procedures, under general anaesthesia, belonging to ASA class I and II were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients aged between 20 to 60 years of both the sex of ASA physical status class I and II, Mallampatti grade I and II undergoing Elective surgeries under general anaesthesia.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with hypertension, cardiac, coronary, renal, hepatic, cerebral diseases, peripheral vascular diseases and electrolyte imbalance, Patients with difficult airway and obese patients or those who require more than one attempt for laryngoscopy and intubation, patients with endocrinal disease like hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, diabetes mellitus, Pregnant and nursing women.

Preoperative assessment

Pre-anaesthetic evaluation was done on the evening before surgery. A routine preanaesthetic examination was conducted assessing and all basic investigations done assessment and investigations. They were informed about the study and an informed consent was taken in all the patients. 100 cases were divided into two groups with 50 cases in each group. Lignocaine group (Group A) Patients received 1.5mg/kg of preservative free 2% lignocaine intravenously 90 seconds before laryngoscopy. Magnesium group (Group B) Patients received 30 mg/kg of magnesium 90 seconds prior to laryngoscopy.

The following cardiovascular parameters were recorded in all patients.

Heart rate [HR] in beats per minute.

Systolic blood pressure [SBP] in mm of Hg

Diastolic blood pressure [DBP] in mm of Hg

Mean blood pressure [MBP] in mm of Hg

The above cardiovascular parameters were monitored in the following time interval of Base line (before giving study drug), Post induction (Pre laryngoscopy) 1,3,5 and 10 min after laryngoscopy and intubation All the patients were pre oxygenated for 3 minutes with 100% oxygen. Induction was achieved with Inj.propofol 2mg/kg i.v and opioid analgesic Fentanyl 2mcg/kg. After checking the ability to ventilate, Inj.vecuronium was administered at a dose of 0.1mg/kg i.v. 3 minutes before laryngoscopy. Randomly selected 50 patients were given IV. Lignocaine 1.5mg/kg and 50 patients were given 30mg/kg magnesium i.v 90 seconds prior to laryngoscopy. Drugs were prepared in a 5 ml syringe by an anaesthesiologist who handed over the syringe in a coded form to the attending anaesthesiologist who records the parameters after injecting the drug. Laryngoscopy was done at the end of 3 mins after vecuronium injection using rigid laryngoscope with standard Macintosh blade. Intubation was done with appropriately sized, disposable, high volume low pressure cuffed endotracheal tube. Laryngoscopy and intubation were done by an experienced anaesthesiologist in all cases. Heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure were recorded post induction and at 1-, 3-, 5- and 10-minute intervals from the onset of laryngoscopy. Patients were connected to closed circuit and anesthesia was maintained with oxygen (50%), air (50%), isoflurane 1% and non-depolarizing muscle relaxant vecuronium bromide at a dose of 0.05 mg/kg i.v. and IPPV. Adequacy of ventilation was monitored by EtCO₂ and SPO₂ was maintained at 99-100%. Positioning and surgery was withheld till the completion of recording upto 10 minutes.

Statistical Methods

In the present study, descriptive statistical analysis was used. Continuous measurement findings are displayed as Mean SD (Min-Max), while categorical measurement results are presented as a number (percent). The significance is determined at a 5% level of significance.

SAS 9.2, SPSS 15.0, Stata 10.1, MedCalc 9.0.1, Systat 12.0, and R environment ver.2.11.1 were used to analyse the data, and Microsoft Word and Excel were used to create graphs, tables, and other images.

Results

Table 1: Gender distribution of patients studied

Gender	Study groups		P-Value
	A	B	
Age in mean years	38.03 (12.84)	39.23 (9.46)	0.60
Male	37 (74%)	35 (70%)	0.55
Female	13 (26%)	15 (30%)	
Total	50	50	100

The above table shows the age distribution in Lignocaine (Group A) and Magnesium (Group B) groups. The age range is 20-60 years in both the groups. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups with regard to age and so they are comparable. ($p=0.60$). Samples are

gender matched with $P=0.55$. In group A 74% of the patients are male and 26% are females. In group B 70% of the patients are males and 30% are females. Both the Groups are comparable with respect to gender.

Table 2: Comparison of Mean Blood Pressure (MBP) (mm Hg) in two groups studied

MBP	Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean difference	95% CI of t		p-value	
						Lower	Upper		
Baseline	B	50	100.42	9.19	3.20	-0.82	7.22	1.58	0.10
	A	50	97.22	7.60					
Post	B	50	91.17	8.13	2.05	-1.55	5.66	1.13	0.25
	A	50	89.11	6.94					
1 min.	B	50	104.66	11.82	-6.02	-11.47	-0.56	-2.20	0.02
	A	50	110.68	11.01					
3 min.	B	50	97.86	8.82	-3.28	-7.73	1.15	-1.47	0.12
	A	50	101.15	9.77					
5 min.	B	50	93.16	7.74	-0.30	-4.16	3.54	-0.15	0.85
	A	50	93.46	8.40					
10 min.	B	50	90.67	7.76	0.76	-2.98	4.52	0.40	0.60
	A	50	89.90	7.95					

Intergroup comparison between the two groups showed that the SBP at 1, 5 and 10 minutes after laryngoscopy in magnesium group were statistically significantly lower compared to lignocaine group ($P<0.05$). At 3-minute SBP was lower in magnesium group but not statistically significant when compared with lignocaine group. In Magnesium group the post induction DBP

values was significantly lower compared to its baseline with P value of 0.02. At 1 minute there was slight increase in mean DBP with $P=0.03$ which returned near baseline value by 3minute. At 5 min and 10 minutes values were significantly lower ($P=0.02$ and $P=0.001$ respectively) when compared to its baseline but this decrease was not clinically significant. Where as in

Lignocaine group statistically significant increase in DBP compared to baseline was seen only at 1 minute after laryngoscopy with P value of <0.001. Intergroup comparison between the two groups showed that the MBP at 1 minute after laryngoscopy in magnesium group was statistically significantly lower compared to lignocaine group (P=0.03). At 3, 5 and 10 minutes MBP was lower in magnesium group but not statistically significant when compared with lignocaine group.

Discussion

One of the commonest modes of securing airway in general anaesthesia is endotracheal intubation. Direct laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation are noxious stimuli and almost always associated with haemodynamic changes due to reflex sympathetic stimulation caused by laryngo-pharyngeal stimulation. [10] Though these changes are usually well tolerated by healthy individuals they can be fatal in patients with hypertension, coronary artery disease and intracranial hypertension. Many pharmacological measures have been used to obtund these responses. Lignocaine has been used both as surface anaesthetic and also by intravenous route to depress haemodynamic response to intubation. [11] Lignocaine, when used systemically, has antagonistic action on sodium channels and NMDA receptors, reduces the release of substance P, has glycinergic action, which decreases the airway reactivity. [12] Magnesium attenuates hemodynamic response by inhibition of catecholamine release from the adrenal medulla and also by reduction of the increased circulating norepinephrine when compared to that of a control group. [13] It also has a systemic and coronary vasodilation effect by antagonizing calcium ion in vascular smooth muscle. [14]

Antihypertensive medicines may cause a decrease in pressor response in patients. Patients taking antihypertensive drugs were excluded from the trial. The medicine

must be effective regardless of patient cooperation, prevent cerebral blood flow disruption, and reduce patient arousal. It should neither be time intensive, nor should it have an impact on the duration and modality of the following anaesthetic. The above criteria appear to be met by intravenous bolus lignocaine and magnesium sulphate. Lignocaine reduces an increase in intracranial pressure and an increase in intraocular pressure associated with laryngotracheal stimulation, in addition to attenuating cardiovascular reactions to laryngoscopy and intubation. Extubation-related cough is also suppressed. For many years, magnesium ions have been recognised to block catecholamine release from both the adrenal glands and peripheral adrenergic nerve terminals. It also causes immediate vasodilation. MgSO₄ has been shown in numerous studies to reduce cardiovascular reactions to endotracheal intubation. [15]

Here an attempt has been made in this study to compare magnesium with lignocaine to find out whether it can be used as a suitable alternative to lignocaine or not. This clinical study is a randomized, prospective, double blind study, was done in 100 patients randomly allocated into two groups. Patients belonging to Group A received 1.5mg/kg of lignocaine intravenously 90 seconds prior to laryngoscopy and intubation. In Group B patients received intravenous magnesium sulphate 30mg/kg 90 seconds prior to laryngoscopy and intubation. James F. Hamill and Robert Bedford F et al used similar dose of lignocaine and found it to be effective in attenuation of sympathetic responses of laryngoscopy and intubation, so dose of 1.5mg/kg of lignocaine was chosen in our study. [16] In 2005, K. Montazeri et al and in 2013, Panda NB et al have done studies on optimal dose of magnesium sulphate for attenuation of hemodynamic response to laryngoscopy and intubation and concluded that 30mg/kg as optimal dose and smaller dose

was less effective and larger doses resulted in complications. [17,18] So 30mg/kg of magnesium sulphate was chosen in our study. Both the groups were well matched for demographic data and no statistically significant difference were found between groups with regard to age and gender.

In magnesium group the mean systolic blood pressure decreased from the baseline to post induction and it was statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) but not clinically significant. After intubation the systolic blood pressure increased at 1 and 3 minutes, this increase from baseline was statistically significant only at 1 min ($P = 0.008$). It gradually reached the below baseline by 5 minutes and was statistically significantly below baseline by 5 min and 10 min ($P = 0.001$ and $P < 0.001$ respectively) however it was not clinically significant. Our results were consistent with study done by Navid nooraei et al in 2013, [14] who noted a similar statistically significant increase in systolic blood pressure in magnesium group only at 1 min ($P = 0.011$) followed by a stable systolic blood pressure as compared to baseline. In our study, mean systolic blood pressure at baseline and post induction were comparable in both lignocaine and magnesium group with P values of 0.29 and 0.39 respectively. At 1-minute systolic blood pressure increased in both lignocaine and magnesium group from baseline but, there was a greater increase of systolic blood pressure in the lignocaine group than magnesium group which was statistically significant with $P = 0.002$. At 3-minute systolic blood pressure in both group were higher compared to baseline but it was not statistically significant ($P = 0.10$). At 5 and 10 min interval systolic blood pressure in both groups were statistically significantly below baseline ($P = 0.001$ and $P = 0.001$ respectively). However, this difference was not clinically significant. Our results were consistent with study done by Navid Nooraei et al in 2013, [14] who noted a similar statistically

significant increase in blood pressure in lignocaine group when compared to magnesium group at 1 min ($P = 0.001$) and 2 min ($P = 0.033$) followed by non-significant difference between two groups at 3, 4 and 5 minutes.

In lignocaine group, mean diastolic blood pressure decreased from baseline after induction, which was not significant both statistically ($P = 0.036$) and clinically. There was statistically significant increase following intubation at 1 min $P < 0.001$ followed by statistically non-significant increase at 3 min and 5 min with $P = 0.08$ and $P = 1.00$ respectively. At 10 minute diastolic blood pressures were below baseline but statistically not significant $P = 1.00$. Our results were consistent with study done by Navid nooraei et al in 2013, [14] who found similar statistically significant increase in diastolic blood pressure at 1 minute ($P = 0.046$) followed by stable DBP. In magnesium group the mean diastolic blood pressure decreased from the baseline to post induction and it was statistically significant ($P = 0.02$) but not clinically significant.

In our study, mean blood pressures at baseline and post induction were comparable in both lignocaine and magnesium group with P values of 0.10 and 0.25 respectively. At 1- minute mean blood pressure increased in both lignocaine and magnesium group from baseline but, there was a greater increase of mean blood pressure in the lignocaine group than magnesium group which was statistically significant with $P = 0.02$. At 3 minute mean blood pressure in both group were higher compared to baseline but it was not statistically significant ($P = 0.12$). At 5 and 10 min interval mean blood pressure in both groups were below baseline but not significant clinically or statistically ($P = 0.85$ and $P = 0.60$ respectively). This was comparable to study done by Navid nooraei et al in 2013, [14] where the Mean blood pressure in the first and second minutes after intubation

was significantly lower in the magnesium group compared to lignocaine group with P values of 0.012 and 0.04 respectively followed by non-statistically significant increase at 3, 4 and 5 minutes. Another similar study conducted in 2005 by K. Montazeri et al, [17] who found that there was statistically significant difference between magnesium and lignocaine groups in mean blood pressure at 1 and 3 minutes after laryngoscopy ($P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.05$ respectively) showing that mean blood pressure was better controlled in magnesium group. In another similar study by Mehrdad Mesbah Kiaee et al, [19] who conducted study in 150 patients undergoing CABG receiving either magnesium sulphate 50mg/kg or lignocaine 1.5mg/kg randomly also showed similar statistically significant difference between lignocaine and magnesium groups in mean blood pressure after intubation ($P = 0.049$) only at 1 minute. [20]

Conclusion

Intravenous lignocaine and intravenous magnesium sulphate both significantly attenuates the sympathetic response to laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation. Intravenous magnesium sulphate at 30mg/kg is more efficient than lignocaine 1.5mg/kg in attenuating the sympathetic response to laryngoscopy and intubation. Hence we conclude that intravenous magnesium sulphate 30mg/kg 90 seconds prior to laryngoscopy and intubation is superior to lignocaine 1.5mg/kg prior to laryngoscopy and intubation.

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